

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7992302>
УДК 616.831-005

INSTRUMENTAL DIAGNOSIS OF ANEURYSMS IN SUBARACHNOID HEMORRHAGES

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Annotation: In the course of the study, the methods of instrumental diagnostics for subarachnoid cerebral hemorrhages were analyzed, a comparative characteristic of the main diagnostic methods, their advantages and disadvantages were carried out.

Keywords: subarachnoid hemorrhages, aneurysms, diagnostics, computed tomography

ИНСТРУМЕНТАЛЬНАЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА АНЕВРИЗМ ПРИ СУБАРАХНОИДАЛЬНЫХ КРОВОИЗЛИЯНИЯХ

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Аннотация: В процессе исследования проанализированы методы инструментальной диагностики при субарахноидальных кровоизлияниях головного мозга, проведена сравнительная характеристика основных методов диагностики, их преимущества и недостатки.

Ключевые слова: субарахноидальные кровоизлияния, аневризмы, диагностика, компьютерная томография

Relevance. A subarachnoid hemorrhage is a sudden bleeding into the subarachnoid space. The most common cause of spontaneous bleeding is aneurysm rupture. Subarachnoid hemorrhage is manifested by a sudden, very pronounced headache, usually with loss or disturbance of consciousness.

According to the frequency of occurrence, subarachnoid hemorrhage ranks third after ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes – the ratio of hemorrhagic, ischemic strokes and subarachnoid hemorrhages per 100 thousand population is 60/30/10, respectively [1]. Subarachnoid hemorrhages account for 4 to 10 % of all forms of acute cerebral circulatory disorders and 8 % of the causes of sudden death due to stroke. The frequency of subarachnoid hemorrhages in the population does not decrease and amounts to 6.4-25 cases per 100 thousand population per year. Studies have shown that 35.7 % of patients with aneurysmal bleeding die or become disabled at the first rupture of aneurysms, 28.6 % – from complications during conservative and surgical treatment. Only 35 % of patients recover, but only one of the 3 survivors regains working capacity equivalent to premorbid [2].

There are several forms of aneurysm localization, but the most common are the following: anterior connective artery – 44.9 %; middle cerebral artery – 21.3 %; internal carotid artery – 24.7 %; posterior connective artery – 3.4 % and vertebral-basilar basin – 5.6 % [2].

In the diagnosis of arterial aneurysms and angiospasm in aneurysmic subarachnoid hemorrhage, X-ray cerebral angiography and its varieties have long been used as the "gold standard": digital subtraction angiography or three-dimensional rotational angiography. But, according to most authors, catheterization angiography continues to be a manipulation associated with a real risk of thromboembolic complications, intimate or total vascular wall dissections [1].

The purpose of the work. To analyze the methods of instrumental diagnostics for subarachnoid cerebral hemorrhages, to conduct a comparative characteristic of the main diagnostic methods, their advantages and disadvantages.

Results and their discussion. A number of instrumental diagnostic methods are used to identify non-traumatic subarachnoid hemorrhage due to

rupture of aneurysms, determine the prognosis of the disease, the likelihood of complications, and develop treatment tactics. Contrast-free CT is often performed; in the absence of changes to CT, a lumbar puncture is performed [3]. Non-contrast CT is performed within 6 hours after the onset of symptoms. MRI is not inferior in sensitivity, but is most often less accessible in emergency situations. If the patient has symptoms of subarachnoid hemorrhage, but there are no changes according to neuroimaging data or its urgent implementation is impossible, then a lumbar puncture is performed. Lumbar puncture is contraindicated if an increase in intracranial pressure is suspected, since a sudden decrease in the pressure of the cerebrospinal fluid can neutralize the tamponing effect of a thrombus on a ruptured aneurysm, provoking further bleeding.

Computed tomography of the brain (CT) is the leading method of diagnosing subarachnoid hemorrhages, especially on the first day of the disease. CT scans determine not only the presence of hemorrhage, but also its intensity, prevalence, presence and volume of intracerebral hematoma and intraventricular hemorrhage, foci of ischemia, severity and nature of hydrocephalus, dislocation syndrome.

In addition, with the help of CT of the brain, it is sometimes possible to establish the true cause of hemorrhage, topographic and anatomical relationships, especially if the study is supplemented with contrast enhancement, 3D reconstruction.

The high informative value of CT scans of the brain and the prognostic significance of the results obtained, the speed of the study make this method mandatory when examining patients with ruptured cerebral aneurysms. The detectability of subarachnoid hemorrhages in the first 12 hours after hemorrhage by CT reaches 95.2 %.

MRI. Verification of aneurysms with magnetic resonance angiography (MR-AG) reaches 80-100 %, which allows in some cases to abandon traditional invasive cerebral angiography, when for some reason it is contraindicated (for example, with individual intolerance to iodine preparations).

In an MRI examination, the hemorrhage looks like hyperintensive (bright) or hypointensive (dark) in the resulting images – depending on the duration of the hemorrhage.

Minor traumatic subarachnoid hemorrhages or minor perimesencephalic hemorrhages have good prognoses with minor long-term

consequences. On the contrary, grade V aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhages have a poor prognosis and require more aggressive treatment [4].

In foreign publications over the past 8-10 years, the results of many studies have been published comparing the diagnostic capabilities of CT angiography, MR angiography, transcranial ultrasound dopplerography and digital subtraction angiography (DSA) in determining cerebral vasospasm in patients with acute subarachnoid hemorrhage on the 5th-10th day from the onset of the disease. The undoubted advantages of CT angiography include minimally invasive, the possibility of carrying out in severe patients, high spatial resolution, the possibility of obtaining three-dimensional models, intracranial vessels, an unlimited number of projections, a short study time, the absence of artifacts from blood flow, lower cost of contrast agents (compared with MRI), the possibility of examining patients with contraindications for MRI. The method makes it possible to obtain important information for a neurosurgeon about the size, direction and shape of the aneurysm body, its anatomical relationships, neck, adjacent arteries, the presence and prevalence of angiospasm. CT angiography, according to a number of authors, has better resolving abilities in the diagnosis of arterial aneurysms compared to MR angiography and surpasses DSA and MRangiography in the diagnosis of small (3-10 mm in diameter) and giant (more than 25 mm) arterial aneurysms. MR angiography has a significant overlap with the DSA data in the diagnosis of spasm relative to the middle and anterior cerebral arteries, and more modest relative.

Conclusions. According to our data, the most significant clinical and instrumental factor in predicting the course and outcome of the disease in patients with acute aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhage is angiospasm, detected during CT angiography.

CT angiography makes it possible to detect angiospasm in the rupture of an arterial aneurysm, starting from the first day of the development of the disease, which makes it an indispensable tool for urgent diagnosis of angiospasm, its causes and associated focal ischemic changes.

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Поступила в редакцию 19.04.2023

Принята к публикации 11.05.2023

Для цитирования:

Aleksandrovich A.S., Zimatkina T.I., Denisiuk M.G., Prihodko A.A. Instrumental diagnosis of aneurysms in subarachnoid hemorrhages // Инновационные научные исследования. 2023. № 5-2(29). С. 40-45. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>